

Genetic Insights into Orthodontics: Exploring the Role of Genomic Variations in Dentofacial Development and Treatment Strategies

Article Type Review Paper

Author Name and Affiliation (In sequence):

Author Sequence	Author Complete Name	Affiliation (Designation, Department, Institution/Organisation Name, City, State, Country)
1	Kanak Priya	Associate Professor, Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopedics, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida
2	Dinesh Kumar Bagga	Professor & Head, Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopedics, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida
3	Poonam Agrawal	Professor, Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopedics, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida
4	Sanjay Kumar	Associate Professor, DST-FIST Facility, Sharda University, Greater Noida
5	Pramod Kumar Mehta	Assistant Professor, Department of Geriatric Medicine, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi.

Corresponding Author Details:

Name: Kanak Priya	Email: dr.kanak.111@gmail.com	Address: Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopedics, School of Dental Sciences, Sharda University, Greater Noida
--------------------------	--------------------------------------	---

Abstract

Genetic insights have reshaped orthodontics by clarifying the role of genomic variations in craniofacial growth and treatment responses. Variations in key genes, including MSX1, DLX5, DLX6, EDN1, PRRX1, and HAND2, are associated with mandibular prognathism, retrognathism, and other craniofacial anomalies. Advanced tools such as linkage analysis, next-generation sequencing, and genome-wide association studies have confirmed the genetic basis of skeletal malocclusions. However, prediction of growth potential remains complex, as genetic influences are modified by epigenetic, hormonal, and environmental factors. Emerging biomarkers from saliva and gingival crevicular fluid provide promising, non-invasive approaches for diagnosis and monitoring. Moreover, gene therapy offers a potential future avenue to enhance tooth movement, bone remodeling, and relapse prevention. Despite current limitations such as small sample sizes and population-specific findings, integrating genetic databases and bioinformatics will enable precision orthodontics, advancing individualized diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment strategies.

Keywords: Genetics, Orthodontics, Craniofacial development, Mandibular growth, Biomarkers, Gene therapy, Precision orthodontics

Introduction

With continuous advancements in the field of genetics, the concepts in orthodontics are constantly evolving. Genes play a crucial role in governing various processes and developments within our bodies, including the growth of craniofacial structures, the formation, and positioning of teeth, as well as the tooth movement induced by orthodontic treatment. Through an understanding of genomic variations, it is now possible to predict certain diseases and malformations before they manifest. Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics is a science that deals with the growth pattern and position of craniofacial structures. The genetic mutations causing variations in mandibular growth and development must be explored in depth to plan future surgery or functional appliance therapy. Any abnormality in the differentiation of the neural crest cells can cause developmental anomalies like frontonasal dysplasia, DiGeorge syndrome, etc. (Babczyńska, Kawala and Sarul, 2022)

Study of the skeletal maturation holds great importance in the field of orthodontics. Despite the genetics governing jaw growth, various appliances have been developed in orthodontics that can control or redirect jaw growth when used during or before pubertal spurt. These appliances reduce the tendency of a skeletal disparity from developing. In order to plan the use of these appliances or chart out further treatment measures, it is important to predict the growth potential of the structures at an early age. CRISPR/Cas-based gene editing has been found to correct genetic causes of craniofacial anomalies. (Nalabothu, Marya and Bhaskar, 2025)

Genetic biomarkers have gained significance in personalized medicine, enabling more precise diagnosis, treatment selection, and disease monitoring. Several genes have been identified that affect the growth of the mandible or maxilla. These include Msh homeobox 1 (MSX1), distal-less homeobox 5 and 6 (DLX5 and DLX6), endothelin 1 (EDN1), paired related homeobox 1 (PRRX1), and heart and neural crest derivatives expressed 2 (HAND2). Any alteration in their sequencing will lead to various syndromes and disease complexes. (Hussein, Porntaveetus and Abid, 2022)

Most of the research on jaw growth is centralized around the development of mandibular prognathism and the genetic factors involved in it. Linkage analysis and twin studies have been carried out for understanding the underlying etiology and develop treatment strategies.

There have been studies on the role of genetics in orthodontics, particularly about malocclusion and craniofacial abnormalities. The genetic etiology of specific orthodontic conditions, such as Class III skeletal pattern and CLP has been proven. Massive parallel sequencing, also known as next-generation sequencing, has been employed in family genetic analysis to formulate the associations between genetic variations and the growth and development of craniofacial structures. These studies have proven the effect of genetic heterogeneity on variations in jaw morphology. Hence, significant exploration of genetic variation and its influence on the development of dentofacial deformities is necessary.

Discussion

- Over the last decade, a diverse range of skeletal prediction methods have been developed. However, the accuracy of these methods has not yet been proven. Growth potential is the increase in size from present to final dimensions which requires precise prediction tools. The methods that have been assessed critically were found to be slow and laborious. The methods are also technique sensitive and owing to the individual variations rely heavily on the expertise of the person determining it. (Sato, Mito and Mitani, 2001)
- Predicting mandible size based solely on genetics is challenging due to the presence of various epigenetic factors such as nutrition, hormonal influences, and functional demands.
- The potential of gene therapy as a novel approach in orthodontic treatment is still unexplored. This research will discover how genetic modifications or interventions can be utilized to enhance tooth movement, promote bone remodeling, or prevent adverse effects associated with orthodontic treatment.
- Studying the genetic factors contributing to post-treatment relapse to identify genetic markers associated with relapse and develop strategies to minimize its occurrence is needed.
- Need to develop comprehensive genomic databases and utilize bioinformatics tools to analyze large-scale genomic data in orthodontics.

Solutions Found

The growth prediction of craniofacial structures has been studied in both animals and humans through various means including cephalometric and genetic methods. Families and siblings are usually analyzed for genetic linkage. There have been genetic association studies and next-generation sequencing analyses for genomes. These studies have led to the identification of multiple genes that are involved in craniofacial development. The following are a few studies involved in studying the growth of jaws.

Analysis of the genetic linkage of bone growth					
S No	Authors	Condition analyzed	Study population	Study method	Result
1.	(El Chekie <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	Mandibular micrognathism	15 cases with mandibular micrognathism and 15 control cases	Whole exome sequencing	Eight new genes (GLUD2, ADGRG4, ARSH, TGIF1, FGFR3, ZNF181, INTS7, and WNT6) were found to be associated with short mandibular length
2.	(Genno <i>et al.</i> , 2019)	Mandibular prognathism	40 cases with mandibular prognathism and 41 control	NGS	C1orf167, NBPF8, and NBPF9 were found to be linked with increased growth of mandible

3.	(Marañón-Vásquez <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Variations in craniofacial dimensions	596 orthodontic patients and 98 patients with craniofacial bone size discrepancy	PCR	GHR rs2973015 was associated with increased lower anterior facial height and mandibular length while IGF2R rs6920141 showed decrease in these.
4.	(Saini, Chowdhry and Mehta, 2022)	Sexual dimorphism in mandibular size	385 adult mandibles	Discriminant function analysis	Mandibular dimensions were found to be greater in males
5.	(Balkhande, Lakkakula and Chitharanjan, 2018)	Mandibular retrognathism	81 patients with mandibular retrognathism and 71 orthognathic controls cases	PCR	MATN1 gene polymorphism is associated with mandibular retrognathism
6.	(Nassif <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Craniofacial malformations (animal study)	Mice	RNA sequencing analysis	Transcription factors expressed in jaw and tibia osteoblasts are associated with craniofacial deformities

7.	(Sieck <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Mandibulofacial dysostosis (MD) (animal study)	6 Hereford calves	Whole genome sequencing	A missense mutation in CYP26C1 causes an increase in retinoic acid and hence causing mandibulofacial dysostosis.
8.	(Yao <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Maxillary deficiency	4 members of a family with skeletal Class III pattern	Whole exome sequencing	ADAMTS2 increases the risk of maxillary deficiency.
9.	(Cooper <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	Mandible size	59 orthodontic patients	RT-PCR	DLX6 and MSX1 are expressed less in retrognathism.
10.	(Kalmari, Arash and Colagar, 2022)	Mandibular prognathism	56 genes found linked with Class III malocclusion due to mandibular prognathism	Web-based tools	PLXNA2, DUSP6, and FBN3 able to predict mandibular prognathism

11.	(Kalmari <i>et al.</i> , 2023)	Mandibular skeletal malocclusions	81 patients depicting skeletal Class III pattern, 82 patients with skeletal Class II pattern and 102 control	PCR-RFLP	COL2A1-G1405S was associated with mandibular retrognathism.
12.	(Tripathi <i>et al.</i> , 2018)	CVMI	150 patients divided into male and female subjects equally	Sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay	IGF-1 and BALP can be used as biomarkers of bone growth

Conclusion

Future Prospective in the Identification of genetic biomarkers

There is a future scope to find the most precise and accurate biomarkers in gingival crevicular fluid (GCF) or saliva that can effectively predict growth patterns and monitor treatment progress.

Future Prospective in gene therapy in Orthodontics

Gene therapy is a highly effective and promising approach in orthodontics. The interrelationships between genetic factors and environmental factors need to be worked upon through next-generation sequencing and other genomic studies. Precision orthodontics can advance treatment and yield outstanding outcomes by providing precise individualized care.

Development of a genetic database on the growth mechanism

The limitations of these studies include the lack of generalizability, limited sample size, and malocclusion-centric nature of research. Hence there is a need to study the correlation between

genotypes and variations in craniofacial structures. A database may be developed with genome-wide association research on the mandibular growth mechanism.

References

- Babczyńska, A., Kawala, B. and Sarul, M. (2022) “Genetic Factors That Affect Asymmetric Mandibular Growth—A Systematic Review,” *Symmetry*, 14(3), p. 490. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym14030490>.
- Balkhande, P.B., Lakkakula, B.V.K.S. and Chitharanjan, A.B. (2018) “Relationship between matrilin-1 gene polymorphisms and mandibular retrognathism,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics: Official Publication of the American Association of Orthodontists, Its Constituent Societies, and the American Board of Orthodontics*, 153(2), pp. 255-261.e1. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2017.06.023>.
- Cooper, R.B.V. *et al.* (2023) “DLX6 and MSX1 from saliva samples as potential predictors of mandibular size: A cross-sectional study,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics: Official Publication of the American Association of Orthodontists, Its Constituent Societies, and the American Board of Orthodontics*, 163(3), pp. 368–377. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2021.12.022>.
- El Chekie, M.R. *et al.* (2023) “Novel genes linked to Class II Division 1 malocclusion with mandibular micrognathism,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics: Official Publication of the American Association of Orthodontists, Its Constituent Societies, and the American Board of Orthodontics*, 163(5), pp. 667-676.e3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2022.04.020>.
- Genno, P. *et al.* (2019) “Three novel genes tied to mandibular prognathism in eastern Mediterranean families,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 156, pp. 104-112.e3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2018.08.020>.
- Hussein, A.S., Porntaveetus, T. and Abid, M. (2022) “The association of polymorphisms in BMP2/MYO1H and skeletal Class II div.1 maxillary and mandibular dimensions. A preliminary ‘report,’” *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 29(10), p. 103405. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2022.103405>.
- Kalmari, A. *et al.* (2023) “Missense polymorphisms potentially involved in mandibular prognathism,” *Journal of Oral Biology and Craniofacial Research*, 13(3), pp. 453–460. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobcr.2023.05.007>.
- Kalmari, A., Arash, V. and Colagar, A.H. (2022) “Influence of COL2A1-G1405S polymorphism on mandibular skeletal malocclusions: A genetic association study and in silico analysis,” *Archives of Oral Biology*, 142, p. 105500. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.archoralbio.2022.105500>.

Marañón-Vásquez, G.A. *et al.* (2020) “GHR and IGF2R genes may contribute to normal variations in craniofacial dimensions: Insights from an admixed population,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 158(5), pp. 722-730.e16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajodo.2019.10.020>.

Nalabothu, P., Marya, A. and Bhaskar, L.V.K.S. (2025) “Gene editing in craniofacial orthodontics,” *British Dental Journal*, 239(2), pp. 83–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41415-025-9020-9>.

Nassif, A. *et al.* (2022) “Transcriptional Regulation of Jaw Osteoblasts: Development to Pathology,” *Journal of Dental Research*, 101(7), pp. 859–869. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/00220345221074356>.

Saini, V., Chowdhry, A. and Mehta, M. (2022) “Sexual dimorphism and population variation in mandibular variables: a study on a contemporary Indian population,” *Anthropological Science*, 130(1), pp. 59–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1537/ase.2108282>.

Sato, K., Mito, T. and Mitani, H. (2001) “An accurate method of predicting mandibular growth potential based on bone maturity,” *American Journal of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics*, 120(3), pp. 286–293. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1067/mod.2001.115932>.

Sieck, R.L. *et al.* (2020) “Mandibulofacial Dysostosis Attributed to a Recessive Mutation of CYP26C1 in Hereford Cattle,” *Genes*, 11(11), p. 1246. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/genes11111246>.

Tripathi, T. *et al.* (2018) “Bone-specific alkaline phosphatase - a potential biomarker for skeletal growth assessment,” *Journal of Orthodontics*, 45(1), pp. 4–10. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14653125.2017.1416571>.

Yao, S. *et al.* (2022) “Skeletal Class III Malocclusion Is Associated with ADAMTS2 Variants and Reduced Expression in a Familial Case,” *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 23(18), p. 10673. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms231810673>.